

Metal Ammine Formation in Solution. Part—XXIII : The Nickel(II)-Mono- and Diethanolamine Systems

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This paper reports a potentiometric and spectrophotometric study of the nickel(II)-mono- and diethanolamine systems. The metal ammine formation was studied by glass electrode measurements in 2 M amHClO₄ and 0.5 M (amH, Na) ClO₄ solutions at 25° and the stability constants determined. The effect of the partly coordinated alcohol groups on the stability constants is considerable. The nickel(II) ion shows little tendency to bind more than two diethanolamine and three monoethanolamine molecules. Spectrophotometric measurements show that aqueous nickel(II) solutions with more than 60 weight per cent of monoethanolamine and pH > 12 have unchanged absorption on further addition of amine. These solutions are presumed to contain a deprotonated species with less than four amino groups bound to nickel.

IN continuation of a paper by Agarwala and Bjerrum¹ on the nickel(II)-triethanolamine system the stability constants of the nickel(II)-mono- and diethanolamine complexes under the same experimental conditions are determined in the present paper. Potentiometric measurements of these systems have previously been made by the Russian authors²⁻⁴ and spectrophotometric measurements in alcoholic and aqueous solutions have also been performed by them⁵⁻⁷. In the present paper spectrophotometric measurements have been made in 2 M ethanolammonium perchlorate solutions and in strong aqueous monoethanolamine solutions with up to 92 weight per cent of the amine.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: All reagents were of analytical grade. The monoethanolamine (Fluca, puriss) was distilled under atmospheric pressure and

the main fraction boiling at 165° was used without further purification. The diethanolamine (Fluca, puriss) was distilled at ~10 mm Hg and the main fraction boiling at 160-163° was used without further purification. The various solutions were prepared in volumetric flasks by weighing or pipetting from stock solutions. 2.50 M stock solution of the ethanolammonium perchlorate was prepared by neutralizing 1 liter 5.00 M HClO₄ with the amine and diluting to 2 liters. Complete equivalence between amine and perchloric acid was ensured as described earlier⁸. All mass action constants are concentration constants (mol/liter units) in the applied medium. Other experimental details were the same as in the preceding paper¹.

Discussion of pH measurements: The results of some of the measured solutions are shown in Table 1. All concentrations are in M/l and the ligand number

TABLE I—SELECTED RESULTS OF GLASS ELECTRODE MEASUREMENTS OF NICKEL(II)-MONO- AND DIETHANOLAMINE PERCHLORATE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

No.	C _{meaH}	C _{Na}	C _{Ni}	C _{mea}	p[mea]	pH	n
1	0.50	0	0.01046	0.00397	3.514	6.326	0.350
2	0.50	0	0.01046	0.0159	2.634	7.206	1.298
3	0.50	0	0.01046	0.0496	1.644	8.196	2.572
4	0.50	0	0.01063	0.0992	1.168	8.672	2.940
5	2.00	0	0.1154	0.0498	3.595	5.905	0.429
6 ^a	2.00	0	0.1154	0.1332	2.990	6.510	1.145
7 ^b	2.00	0	0.1154	0.1663	2.814	6.686	1.428
8	2.00	0	0.1154	0.3322	1.637	7.863	2.679
9	2.00	0	0.1154	0.4155	1.187	8.313	3.037
	C _{deaH}	C _{Na}	C _{Ni}	C _{dea}	p[dea]	pH	n
10	0.100	0.400	0.0115	0.00536	2.960	5.980	0.370
11	0.100	0.400	0.0115	0.00965	2.631	7.309	0.636
12	0.100	0.400	0.0115	0.0268	1.924	8.016	1.296
13	0.100	0.400	0.0115	0.0386	1.680	8.260	1.530
14	0.50	0	0.0115	0.00643	2.858	6.372	0.438
15	0.50	0	0.0115	0.0107	2.570	6.660	0.697
16	2.00	0	0.0577	0.0215	3.380	5.650	0.365
17	2.00	0	0.0577	0.0322	3.107	5.923	0.545
18	2.00	0	0.0577	0.0859	2.248	6.782	1.391
19	2.00	0	0.0577	0.1502	1.409	7.621	1.927

^a Calcd. $\alpha_0 = 0.22$, $\alpha_1 = 0.47$, $\alpha_2 = 0.29$, $\alpha_3 = 0.03$, $\bar{n} = 1.14$

^b Calcd. $\alpha_0 = 0.13$, $\alpha_1 = 0.42$, $\alpha_2 = 0.39$, $\alpha_3 = 0.06$, $\bar{n} = 1.38$

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is calculated from the expression

$$\bar{n} = (C_{\text{am}} - [\text{am}] + [\text{H}^+])/C_{\text{Ni}}$$

where C_X represents the stoichiometric concentration of the species X. In Fig. 1 the formation curves are

Fig. 1. Formation curves ($\bar{n}$ vs $p[\text{am}]$) at 25° for the three nickel(II)-ethanolamines. Experimental and calculated values for nickel(II)-mono- and diethanolamine in 0.5 M (amH,Na)ClO₄ and 2 M amHClO₄, compared with the calculated curve for nickel(II)-triethanolamine in 0.5 M and 2 M teaHClO₄,¹ and with the nickel(II)-ammonia system in 0.5 M and 2 M NH₃NO₃ at 25°. Signs used for 2 M amHClO₄: ○ ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.01-0.02$ M), ● ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.04-0.1$ M), and ⊙ ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.005$ M). Signs for 0.5 M amHClO₄: □ ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.01-0.02$ M), ⊞ ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.04$ M) and ⊚ ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.005$ M) and for 0.1 M amHClO₄, 0.4 NaClO₄: △ ($C_{\text{Ni}} \sim 0.01-0.02$ M).

plotted for the nickel(II)-monoethanolamine (mea) and diethanolamine (dea) systems in 0.5 M (amH, Na)ClO₄ and 2 M amHClO₄ solutions. For purposes of comparison, the curves determined by Agarwala and Bjerrum are also drawn for the triethanolamine system and those for the nickel(II)-ammonia system in 0.5 M and 2 M NH₃NO₃ at 25°. The ethanolammonium concentrations are varied in the 0.5 M (amH, Na)ClO₄ solutions as seen from Table 1 and indicated by the signs of the points in Fig. 1. Contrary to the triethanolamine system,¹ the influence of changing the meaH⁺ and deaH⁺ concentrations is found to be negligible. A change in C_{Ni} , from 0.005 to ~0.1 M also has no influence on the formation curves within the uncertainty of the experiments. It can, therefore, be concluded that the metal ammine formation in the Ni(II)-mea and Ni(II)-dea systems is not interfered by hydrolysis and polymerization reactions.

The full drawn curves in Fig. 1 are calculated on the basis of the estimated constants shown in Table 2. The constants determined by the Russian authors^{2,8,10} are also shown for comparison. The values determined by Sychev and Gerbeleu for the Ni(II)-mea⁸ and Ni(II)-tea¹⁰ systems are in reasonably good agreement with our values apart from their value for K_3 in the Ni(II)-tea system which should have been corrected for hydrolysis. On the other hand, the values presented by Sklenskaya and Karapet-yants² for all three ethanolamines are not reliable.

The amines are bound to the metal through the nitrogen atom but it is obvious that the alcohol groups also take part in the complex formation. The large values of the ratios between successive constants and the decreasing number of ligands taken up with increasing number of ligands involved show directly that chelation plays a role. It is therefore reasonable to assume that Ni(mea)₃²⁺ and Ni(dea)₃²⁺ to some extent, are octahedral complexes with three chelate bound, respectively two tridentate bound ligands. The small tendency of these complexes to take up further ligands and of Nitea²⁺ to take up a second ligand supports these assumptions. However, the coordination of the alcohol groups must be weak for it had no observable effect on the enthalpy changes. Sychev and

TABLE 2—THE DETERMINED STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR THE THREE NICKEL(II)-ETHANOLAMINE SYSTEMS AND THE PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF THE AMINES IN ETHANOLAMMONIUM SALT SOLUTIONS AT 25°

	Mea			Dea			Tea		
	0.4 ^a	0.5 ^a	2 ^a M	0.43 ^a	0.5 ^a	2 ^a M	0.5 ^a	0.5 ^b	2 ^b M
pK_{amH}	—	9.54	9.80	9.09	8.93	9.32	—	7.90	8.32
$\log K_1$	3.06	3.12	3.32	3.31	2.60	3.00	—	2.85	3.42
$\log K_2$	2.46	2.56	2.78	2.13	1.87	2.27	0.82	0.14	—
$\log K_3$	1.43	1.80	2.00	1.42?	—	—	—	—	—
$\log \beta_3$	—	(0.32)	(0.40)	—	—	—	—	—	—
$\log \beta_2$	5.52	5.68	6.10	—	4.47	5.27	—	2.99	4.29
$\log \beta_1$	6.95	7.48	8.10	—	—	—	—	—	—
$\log \beta_0$	—	(7.80)	(8.50)	—	—	—	—	—	—

^a Values determined in this paper.

^b Values determined by Agarwala and Bjerrum¹ in 0.5 M (teaH, Na)ClO₄ and 2 M teaHClO₄.

^c Values determined by Sychev and Gerbeleu⁸ in 0.4 M (meaH, K)NO₃ at 25°.

^d Values determined by Sychev, Gerbeleu and Migal¹⁰ in 0.5 M (teaH, K)NO₃ at 25°.

^e Values determined by Sklenskaya and Karapet-yants² in 0.43 M (deaH, K)NO₃ at 25°.

Gerbeleu^{9,10} have determined the enthalpy changes in the Ni(II)-mea system and found for the uptake of the first three ligands $-\Delta H_1=3.35$, $-\Delta H_2=3.90$ and $-\Delta H_3=2.60$ kcal/mol, and for the first ligand in the Ni(II)-tea system $-\Delta H_1=3.86$ kcal/mol. These values are of the same order as the average value 3.5 kcal/mol for the uptake of an NH_3 -molecule in the Ni(II), NH_3 system^{9,11}.

Finally it should be noticed that the influence of the ethanolammonium concentrations on pK_{amH} and the stability constants is unusually high and increases in the order $\text{tea} > \text{dea} > \text{mea} > \text{NH}_3$ (cf. Fig. 1 and Table 2).

Discussion of Ni(II)-mea spectra : Fig. 2 shows the absorption (ϵ , λ)-curves in the visible range for Ni(II)-mea solutions in 2 M meaHClO_4 (curves 4-7) with $\bar{n}$ varying from 0 to 1.42. On the basis of these data the position of the absorption maximum

Fig. 2. Spectra (ϵ , λ) of nickel(II)-monoethanolamine perchlorate solutions at 22-23°. The composition of the solutions are as follows :

1. $C_{Ni} = 0.0418$ M, $C_{mea} = 15.29$ M (92%).
2. $C_{Ni} = 0.0418$ M, $C_{mea} = 5.32$ M.
3. $C_{Ni} = 0.0418$ M, $C_{mea} = 1.33$ M.
4. Sol. 7 in Table 1. $\bar{n} = 1.428$.
5. Sol. 6 in Table 1. $\bar{n} = 1.145$.
6. $C_{meaH} = 2.00$, $C_{Ni} = 0.1154$, $C_{mea} = 0.0200$, $\bar{n} = 0.173$.
7. $C_{meaH} = 2.00$, $C_{Ni} = 0.1154$, $pH \sim 2$, $\bar{n} = 0$, Estimated for ϵ_1 - - - - -

of the mono-amine complex is estimated to be $\lambda_{max}(\epsilon_1) = 642$ nm. This is a blue shift of 18 nm compared to that of the aqua nickel(II) ion with $\lambda_{max}(\epsilon_0) = 660$ nm. A blue shift of this magnitude agrees well with what is found in the Ni(II)-tea⁹ and in the Ni(II)- NH_3 system⁹.

The curves 1-3 in Fig. 2 show the absorption spectra of aqueous monoethanolamine nickel(II) perchlorate solutions with $C_{mea} = 15.29$, 5.32 and 1.33 M/l, respectively. Solutions with $C_{mea} = 10.64$ and 11.97 M/l were also measured but their absorption curves were so close to that of the limiting curve with λ_{max} at 595 nm (and 92 weight per cent of monoethanolamine) that they are not plotted in the figure. Measurements were also made of two solutions with $C_{mea} \sim 10$ M/l and added strong base : $C_{NaOH} = 0.04$ and 0.4 M/l. The first solution had practically the same λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} as the limiting curve, but for the stronger basic solution a small red shift of λ_{max} to 605 nm and a decrease of ϵ_{max} from 10.0 to 8.8 were observed. The blue shift of λ_{max} from the aqua nickel ion to λ_{max} of the limiting curve is therefore found to be $660 - 595 = 65$ nm. From this estimate it can be concluded that at the most $65/18 \approx 3.6$ amine groups can be coordinated to the nickel ion. In these solutions with $pH > 12$ it is reasonable to assume that deprotonated species such as $\text{Ni}(\text{mea})_2^-$ are dominating. In solutions of higher basicity, it is possible that the amine ligands are exchanged with hydroxyl ions. The small red shift observed when the added concentration of NaOH is increased from 0.04 to 0.4 M/l seems to support this assumption.

References

1. B. V. AGARWALA and J. BJERRUM, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1982, A 36, 459.
2. A. YA. SYCHEV and A. P. GERBELEU, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 7, 138.
3. E. V. SKLENSKAYA and M. KH. KARAPET-YANTS, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 11, 1478.
4. S. V. GORBACHEV, T. G. MARCHENKOVA and E. G. TIMOFEEVA, *Koord. Khim.*, 1977, 3, 802.
5. V. V. UDOVENKO and YU. S. DUECHINSKII, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 11, 1481; 1967, 12, 517.
6. YU. S. DUEBHINSKII, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 13, 974.
7. G. J. GALKINA and E. G. TIMOFEEVA, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 14, 1745.
8. L. ILICHEVA and J. BJERRUM, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1976, A 30, 343.
9. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, 1941, reprinted 1957.
10. A. YA. SYCHEV, A. P. GERBELEU and P. K. MIGAL, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 8, 1081.
11. I. POULSEN and J. BJERRUM, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 1407.